

Lowland rice field weeds in Nueva Ecija, Philippines

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We surveyed rice field weeds in barangays Malimba, Mangino, Santa Cruz, and Santo Cristo Norte of Gapan, Nueva Ecija, in Feb 1984. Seventy-eight randomly selected fields were visited during heading to flowering after weed control; 66 were wet seeded (pregerminated seed sown on puddled soil) and 12 were transplanted. The percentage cover was determined visually for all weed species.

Twenty-six weed species of 21 genera and 13 families were identified (see table). Fifty percent of the weed species belonged to Poaceae and Cyperaceae. Seventeen species were found in transplanted rice and 25 in wet seeded rice; 16 were common to both cultures. *Echinochloa colona* was the only species in transplanted rice that was not found in wet seeded rice.

E. glabrescens was observed in all the fields surveyed. *Monochoria vaginalis* occurred in 77% of the fields, *Fimbristylis miliacea* in 59%, and *Paspalum distichum* in 58%. For three of these species, infestation was greater

Percentage of fields^a infested with weeds and the severity of infestation in transplanted and wet seeded rice in Gapan, Nueva Ecija, Philippines.

Weed species	Family	Transplanted (12)		Wet seeded (66)	
		Fields infested (%)	Cover (%)	Fields infested (%)	Cover (%)
<i>Echinochloa glabrescens</i> Munro ex Hook. f.	Poaceae	100	9	100	21
<i>Monochoria vaginalis</i> (Burm. f.) Presl	Pontederiaceae	92	7	74	12
<i>Fimbristylis miliacea</i> L.	Cyperaceae	50	8	61	18
<i>Paspalum distichum</i> L.	Poaceae	50	7	59	6
<i>Scirpus supinus</i> L.	Cyperaceae	8	45	56	21
<i>Ludwigia octovalvis</i> (Jacq.) Raven	Onagraceae	50	1	39	2
<i>Lindernia anagallis</i> (Burm. f.) Pinnell	Scrophulariaceae	25	39	42	12
<i>Eclipta alba</i> (L.) Hassk.	Asteraceae	33	<1	24	7
<i>Cyperus difformis</i> L.	Cyperaceae	17	3	30	3
<i>Cyperus rotundus</i> L.	Cyperaceae	17	<1	26	14
<i>Marsilea minuta</i> L.	Marsileaceae	33	18	21	22
<i>Cyperus iria</i> L.	Cyperaceae	33	11	21	4
<i>Hedyotis corymbosa</i> (L.) Lam.	Rubiaceae	17	21	21	10
<i>Sphenoclea zeylanica</i> Gaertn.	Sphenocleaceae	8	<1	18	1
<i>Paspalum scrobiculatum</i> L.	Poaceae	—	—	14	4
<i>Ischaemum rugosum</i> Salisb.	Poaceae	—	—	9	6
<i>Ipomoea aquatica</i> Forsk	Convolvulaceae	8	<1	6	<1
<i>Portulaca oleracea</i> L.	Portulacaceae	8	15	6	<1
<i>Eichhornia crassipes</i> (Mart.) Solms	Pontederiaceae	—	—	8	2
<i>Echinochloa colona</i> (L.) Link	Poaceae	25	10	—	—
<i>Echinochloa crus-galli</i> (L.) Beauv. ssp. <i>hispidula</i> (Retz.) Honda	Poaceae	—	—	5	<1
<i>Alternanthera sessilis</i> (L.) Dc.	Amaranthaceae	—	—	3	17
<i>Sphaeranthus africanus</i> L.	Asteraceae	—	—	3	<1
<i>Commelina diffusa</i> Burm. f.	Commelinaceae	—	—	3	<1
<i>Fimbristylis acuminata</i> Vahl	Cyperaceae	—	—	2	<1
<i>Fuirena ciliaris</i> (L.) Roxb.	Cyperaceae	—	—	2	<1

^a Number of fields surveyed is in parentheses.

in wet seeded than in transplanted rice.

In addition to weed species that commonly occur in wet seeded and transplanted rice, we identified the

following potential problem weeds:

Scirpus supinus, *Lindernia anagallis*, and *Marsilea minuta*. *♂*

Pest Control and Management

OTHER PESTS

Bird damage to rice in Visveswaraiah Canal Tract (VCT)

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Birds *Ploceus philippinus* L. (baya weaver bird), *P. manyar* Horsfield (streaked weaver bird), *Lonchura striata* L. (whitebacked munia), *L. malacca* L. (black-headed munia), *L. punctulata* L. (spotted munia), and *Estrilda amandava* L. (red munia) feed on rice grains in VCT, Mandya. We recorded bird

Table 1. Feeding rate, flock size, and abundance of rice birds, VCT, Mandya,^a India.

Bird	Feeding rate (pecks/min) ($\bar{x} \pm$ SD)	Flock size (max - min)	Population (%)	Habitat preference
Streaked weaver bird	8.2 ± 2.4	46-15	69	Wet
Baya weaver bud	6.0 ± 0.9	17-4	8	Wet
Blackheaded munia	6.0 ± 1.7	33-14	19	Wet
Whitebacked munia	3.0 ± 1.0	3-2	<1	Dry
Spotted munia	2.5 ± 1.2	5-2	<1	Dry
Red munia	3.6 ± 0.8	9-3	3	Wet
CD at 5% by 'F' test	ns	ns	18	—

^a Numbers in a column are ± of 15 observations recorded from fields adjacent to patches of marsh and sugarcane.

populations, feeding rate, and habitat preference in rice fields in May-Jun 1985

and calculated the relative economic importance of each species.

Streaked weaver bird, which prefers a wet habitat, was the most abundant and most serious pest (Table 1). Red munia was the least serious pest. Whitebacked munia and spotted munia preferred dry conditions, and caused little damage.

VCT has large areas of rice fields interspersed with sugarcane fields at a 5:1 ratio, and 0.5 to 1 ha marshy patcher covered with *Typha* sp. The patches of sugarcane and the marsh determined bird distribution and concentration because they provide roosting, nesting, and shelter. We therefore recorded panicle damage in rice fields at various

Table 2. Panicle damage^a on rice fields at various distances from marsh and sugarcane, VCT, Mandya, India.

Time	Panicle damage (%)					
	Among fields ^b			Within a field ^c		
	< 10 m	10 to 20 m	> 20 m	Edge	Center	Rear
May 1985	37	0	0	45	<1	<1
May 1985	35	0	0	47	<1	<1

^aAt each location, ± panicle damage is from 15 randomly chosen units. ^bDistances from patches of marsh and sugarcane. ^cEdge = 4 rows adjacent to marsh or sugarcane plot; centre = in between edge and rear; rear = last 4 rows of rice from marsh or sugarcane.

distances from marshland and sugarcane fields. Table 2 shows that 35-37% of bird damage was within 10 m of

sugarcane and marsh. Damage was greatest in rice immediately adjacent to sugarcane and marsh. *J*

Soil and Crop Management

Nutrient management in late kharif rice

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We studied nutrient management in late kharif rice at TNAU in 1975. Soil had pH 8.1, ECe 0.2 mmho/cm, low N, high P and K, 88 ppm Fe, and 4 ppm Zn. All plots received the recommended 120-26.4-50.4 kg NPK/ha. The experiment was in split-plot design with IR8, IR20, and Bhavani each sown in main plots on 15 Aug, 1 Sep, and 15 Sep. Subplots were control, 30 kg N/ha, 30-6.6 kg NP/ha, 50 kg ferrous sulfate/ha, and 50 kg ferrous sulfate and 25 kg Zn sulfate/ha.

Grain yield decreased when sowing was later than 15 Aug (see table). The 15 Aug crop had greater leaf area index, longer panicles, and more filled spikelets than other crops. IR20 yielded more than Bhavani and IR8 in the 15 Sep sowing. Applying Fe and Zn increased yield 20% over that of the control. Sowing date and fertilizer application were not significantly interactive, indicating that grain yield of the 15 Sep crop would not reach that of the 15 Aug crop, even with additional fertilizer application. *J*

Influence of sowing date, variety, and fertilization on grain yield in Tamil Nadu, India.

Sowing date	Variety	Yield (t/ha)					Mean
		30 kg N	30 kg N 6.6 kg P	50 kg ferrous sulfate	50 kg ferrous sulfate 25 kg Zn sulfate	Control	
15 Aug	IR8	4.5	4.3	3.9	4.4	3.5	4.1
	IR20	4.6	4.7	4.9	5.1	4.3	4.8
	Bhavani	5.0	5.0	5.0	5.5	4.7	5.0
	Mean	4.7	4.7	4.6	5.0	4.1	4.6
1 Sep	IR8	2.5	2.0	1.9	2.4	2.2	2.2
	IR20	2.8	2.6	2.9	3.0	2.5	2.8
	Bhavani	3.2	3.3	3.0	3.6	2.7	3.2
	Mean	2.8	2.6	2.6	3.0	2.5	2.7
15 Sep	IR8	0.9	0.9	1.0	1.4	0.8	1.0
	IR20	2.7	2.9	2.8	3.0	2.6	2.8
	Bhavani	1.7	2.1	1.8	2.2	1.9	1.9
	Mean	1.8	1.9	1.9	2.2	1.8	1.9
Sowing dates		CD (P = 0.05)					
Varieties		216					
Ameliorative treatments		173					
Sowing date × variety interaction		373					

Sowing date for photoperiod-sensitive Caribe 7

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Caribe 7 grows in low-lying fields where deep water may prevent other varieties from being grown. It is photoperiod

Performance of Caribe 7 at different sowing dates, Havana, Cuba.

Date	Yield ^a (t/ha)
15 Apr	4.5 ab
15 May	4.4 b
15 Jun	5.5 a
15 Jul	2.5 c

^aMeans followed by a common letter are not significantly different (P = 0.05).